

AI and connectivity for sustainable and efficient transportation – the EcoMobility approach

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Abstract—Connectivity is a game changer for smart mobility by enabling the automated sharing of information among the stakeholders. This, in turns, enables to bridge the silos and create comprehensive understanding of the full environment and all participants, finally acting as foundation for the uptake of innovative services. Target of this paper is to present the three pilots related to door-to-door multimodal transportation in densely populated cities developed in the context of the EcoMobility program. More especially, this paper will discuss how the proposed key digital enablers (navigation, HD map and VRU detection - all enabled by connectivity) will provide a technology basis to disrupt the respective application domains.

Keywords— Connectivity, CCAM, energy efficiency, road safety

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is rapidly transforming with new technologies, emphasizing smart cities and shared transportation infrastructures. This shift demands a new digital mobility platform. Innovations like AI, IoT, and automation are reshaping business models and promoting coordinated transportation. Door-to-door mobility complexity is rising, necessitating a stable digital value chain. The vehicle, evolving into an "Internet node on wheels," exchanges data

Fig. 1 Digital transformation toward service-centric, connected mobility ecosystem

with diverse vehicles, emphasizing road safety. Addressing these challenges requires cross-disciplinary solutions and methods, ensuring interaction throughout the development process while meeting safety requirements for embedded real-time systems.

The main aim of the EU funded project EcoMobility is to create a sustainable value chain and enabling technologies for door-to-door mobility. The goal is to address urban challenges like traffic congestion and Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection using AI and Smart Cities methodologies. The solutions support the transition from isolated transportation to a connected, service-centric mobility ecosystem. Four key digital enablers – AI, safety, robust architecture, and digital agility – impact technology adoption and determine the intelligent mobility solution's effectiveness in addressing digitalization and ecological challenges. The aim is to provide added value to water and road operations, ultimately improving the efficiency and safety of urban transportation systems.

Target of the paper is to present three core technologies (navigation, digital map and accident prevention for VRU) and their deployment in relevant industrial use cases to improve transportation efficiency, enhance safety measures, promote multimodal transport integration, and leverage advanced technologies to meet the challenges of modern urban mobility.

II. AI AND CONNECTIVITY FOR URBAN MOBILITY

A. Navigation and Path Planning Technologies

Autonomous and tele-operated robotic platforms are witnessing an unparallel expansion in recent years, due to advances in robotics, automation, and cognitive research fields, including computer vision, machine learning, sensor fusion, obstacle recognition, and planning. These tools can operate with greater efficiency and lower cost while they can complete complex tasks without the risk of human life.

Various robotic platforms or unmanned-x-vehicles (UxV) in different operational mediums including air (UAV), ground (UGV), underwater (UUV), or surface (USV) have been extensively employed for various real-life applications. One particular challenge for autonomous robotic platforms is their navigation in unknown and unpredictable environments [1]. As such, global path planning involves determining an optimal route starting position to its destination while considering the characteristics of the environment. The robotic platform utilises data obtained from the sensing devices carried by the robot to achieve completely independent decisions through online processing. At the same advanced algorithms, such Reinforcement Learning (RL) are often employed to allow them to perceive their surroundings and adapt their trajectories in real-time based on changing environmental conditions. Numerous approaches and techniques have been recently proposed in the field of underwater motion planning for AUVs. Graph search algorithms like A* or Dijkstra's algorithm utilises a grid-based graph representation, where vertices correspond to specific polygons within the grid, and edges denote direct paths, providing a structured framework for navigation [2][3]. These methods are simple and easy to implement, have lower computation complexity, and therefore are ideal for small scale maps. Another category, evolutionary algorithms, such as the GA, PSO and QPSO offer a promising approach to underwater path planning, leveraging principles inspired by natural selection and evolution to efficiently navigate the complex and dynamic underwater environment [4]. Evolutionary algorithms are very efficient for navigation in high-dimensional search spaces, although in some cases their iterative nature may require significant computational resources and time to converge on optimal solutions, potentially limiting their real-time applicability. An emerging discipline within artificial intelligence, RL has been increasingly used in the control design and path planning of robots. The R approach encompasses one or more agents engaging in real-time interactions with an environment that is often expressed based on Markov processes [5]. Based on their experience, the agents learn to select optimal strategies to reach a specific target and maximise their cumulative rewards, so that if an action improves performance, the desire to perform that action is reinforced. Numerous recent studies have employed RL methods for autonomous navigation [6][7][8].

B. AI for high-definition digital maps

High-definition digital map is key to enable efficient, precise and reliable solutions to door-to-door transportation, traffic management models and perception algorithms. Data quality and quantity is crucial because it directly impacts the performance, accuracy, and reliability of AI models. At the same time, the gathering of sufficient datasets of diverse real-world ensembles in a wide variety of situations in terms of quality, diversity, and quantity is challenging. To resolve this lack of relevant data, the necessary synthetic data will be generated to improve the performance of AI models and algorithms to make the necessary decisions that enable safe mobility in smart cities. Beside the quantity and the quality of the data – as key factor for the efficient training of the models – another key factor is the proper and consistent data format, as well as calibration and synchronization between the components. On one hand, intrinsic and extrinsic calibration of sensors allows for obtaining measurements closer to reality

and associating the information received by the sensors with global coordinates, respectively [9]. On the other hand, synchronization ensures that all measurements are correctly referenced in a common temporal framework for all system agents. As a result, we obtain a series of detections made by different sensors and from different agents that are referenced to the same global position, and time coordinates encapsulated in high-quality 2D and 3D maps that are updated in real-time.

One key technology involved is the development of Digital Twins (DTs) for Smart City traffic management to replicate real assets and testing different scenarios and regimes. Our target is to improve simulation engines used for autonomous driving to generate traffic models of trajectories to be followed by the automobiles when running into the Smart City, while integrating models of the connected vehicle, of the infrastructure and of the road users in general. Traffic models depending on key information received from traffic data and digital maps. We refer to a model for predictive Smart City traffic interacting dynamically with the environment and surroundings (On-Line basis) and not following pre-established patterns or pre-conceived paths. We are developing Machine and Deep Learning algorithms to enable the models making their own decisions and act autonomously suggesting to drivers the best alternatives to drive through and enhancing urban mobility providing society with efficient and safe multimodal transportation systems. A true challenge of the technology is the reliable and efficient gathering of real data to feed the digital twins and traffic models. The approach is to use high bandwidth, low latency 5G New Radio C-V2X communications featured with the ETSI Collective Perception (CP) service standard [10] to upload and collect sensor perceptions from vehicles and fixed Road Side Units (RSU). The object perceptions will be stored in a database located on the edge/cloud to be available for the data consumer subsystems. From the authors knowledge this is the first time that CP service will be used to collect perceptions to feed digital twins or traffic models. One of the main challenge in the use of vehicular communications is the accuracy of the geolocation attached to V2X messages. In order to ensure reliable digital twins and traffic models, the Collective Perception Messages include geolocation by the use of Real Time Kinematic differential corrections enabling centimetric accuracy and making the whole system robust to the most common issues of GNSS geolocation such as multipath.

C. Accident Prevention for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)

Accident prevention for VRUs can be significantly improved integrating connected vehicles and users' perception relying on roadside cameras. Relying on the combination of a distributed network of heterogeneous IoT devices (e.g., smart camera, connected vehicles and localization systems) and a widespread connectivity infrastructure, and edge servers, the system will be able to precisely locate moving physical assets (specifically, pedestrians and vulnerable users) and provide the obtained data to cars and road users in real-time (as if the location of physical assets would come directly from the sensors of the receiving device). This will allow connected cars and road users to perceive the environment from multiple point-of-view (depending on installed cameras and road-side units) and provide a much-increased awareness of the nearby environment [11].

Fig. 2 illustrates the scenario: a road users hidden by another car is seen by roadside camera. The application

predicts a possible collision, and an alert is sent to the driver. Similarly, the VRU can be alerted via suitable mobile and wearable devices. This scenario implies developing low-latency perception and communication technologies to provide alerts in time for the user, or car advanced driver assistant system (ADAS) to intervene. In particular, we will focus on two key technologies: (1) Embedded real-time object detection running on smart cameras to detect users and communicate only relevant metadata [12]; (2) 5G communication technologies and multi access-edge computing 5G MEC to compute and communication predicted collision with low latency [13].

Fig. 2 Accident Prevention for Vulnerable Road Users.

This use case will rely on the existing Modena Automotive Smart Area (MASA, **Error! Reference source not found.**): a project, created through a public-private partnership, aiming to develop a living lab to test, evaluate, and implement Cooperative Connected and Autonomous Mobility (CCAM), on different environments (a proving ground and a real-life urban area).

III. EcoMObility smart city pilots

In the following, the use cases supporting the deployment and evaluation of the proposed technologies described in Section 2 are presented. Navigation and path planning technologies are applied to the smart mobility use case, marking a significant step towards a sustainable, efficient, and environmentally friendly multi-modal transportation system for urban areas. AI for high-definition digital maps is applied in the door-to-door transportation to reduce traffic congestion, and optimize transportation systems. Accident prevention for VRUs is applied in the Smart city and users in the loop use case, increasing the safety of the user providing timely alerts to the city users.

A. Smart mobility with Multi-modal autonomous & tele-operated transport on land and sea

Industrial Pilot 1 focuses on developing a multi-modal transport system for metropolitan areas, integrating autonomous and tele-operated land and marine transport. This approach addresses the problems caused by urban congestion and the need for sustainable transport solutions. The objectives of this effort are to reduce traffic jams, increase productivity, and improve citizens' overall mobility experience. Pilot 1 integrates sea vessels, rental passenger cars, and shared e-scooters into an autonomous and tele-operated driving system, leveraging 5G connectivity and B5G holographic communication technology. The pilot comprises two sub-use cases: (a) Autonomous and Tele-operated Land and Sea Assets and Precise Localization during Difficult

Manoeuvring, focusing on the tele-operation of land and sea assets, ensuring precise localization during challenging manoeuvres; (b) Holographic Communication Supported by 360 Perception and Operator Assistance on Cars and Sea Vessels, emphasising on the use of holographic communication to enhance operator assistance and perception on both land and sea vehicles.

Fig. 3 Industrial Pilot 1 use cases

Autonomous and tele-operated sea vessels, tele-operated cars, and tele-operated e-scooters will be developed and demonstrated. 5G connectivity and holographic communication will be utilised for these developments, ensuring low latency, high bandwidth, and reliable data transfer. Radar-based navigation will be used for precise sea vessel localization to be able to operate in cases of sea clutter and harsh weather conditions. With the implementation of autonomous and tele operated e-scooters in the pilot, the use case will also be validated for last mile transport improving its access and availability, therefore improving connection to other transport modes. Pilot 1 represents a significant step towards creating a sustainable and efficient multi-modal transportation system for urban areas. It aims to reduce reliance on personal vehicles in urban areas, promote shared services, and reduce carbon emissions. By utilising advanced technologies such as 5G and holographic communication, this pilot demonstrates different options for safe, efficient, and environmentally friendly transport solutions.

B. AI for efficient door 2 door transportation

Industrial Pilot 2 focuses on leveraging advanced digitization and artificial intelligence for a high-definition digital mapping system. This system, integrated with autonomous vehicles' sensors and telemetry, creates digital twins of road environments. First step is related to communication, consisting in a TCU featured with 5G New Radio and C-V2X, high accuracy GNSS and an own developed Stack C-V2X with Collective Perception service [15], as well as a database to store the data and create the digital twins and traffic models of the technology. Perception algorithms as well as precise calibration and synchronization systems for sensors embedded in both mobile and infrastructure agents are unified under a common global reference system in terms of position and time and presented using high-quality 2D and 3D maps in real time. This information will be used for the development of AI models and enhanced annotated datasets that will help to improve and adapt perception algorithms to the target domain of the smart city. The target is to predict what will happen in the near future and enable the city to adapt its development accordingly, finally increasing user-friendliness. Realistic traffic models are going to be used to mitigate the problems derived from the high demand of private vehicles, based on the data collected by the own road users and infrastructures, taking advantage of HD digital maps. Realistic and reliable digital twins are a powerful technological tool to accelerate developments in intelligent mobility.

The expected impact and results can be stated as follows: (a) Innovation and efficiency improvement: Digital twins enhancing and complementing realistic traffic models with environmental (real) and synthetic (virtual) data giving exploitation of multimodal transportation systems and improvement of urban mobility and lessening the ill-effects of jams and bottlenecks; (b) Process improvement through real-time update of available traffic models can establish, finally, transportation as a service (TaaS); (c) Cost reduction by reduction of energy consumption, CO2 footprint and traffic accidents through the development of efficient multimodal door-to-door transportation networks optimizing vehicle delays and, for instance, traffic lights synchronization; (d) new business generation supported by innovative solutions for the development of intelligent, efficient, sustainable and safe mobility within the progress of smart cities.

C. Smart city and users in the loop

The industrial Pilot 3 pursues the goal of improving the safety of VRU in an urban environment. The widespread use and misuse of mobile phones is one of the main reasons accountings for such a trend. The idea is to demonstrate improvements with respect to the State of Art (SoA), in both safety of the intended functionality (SOTIF), and functional safety (FS), by enhancing the above mentioned large widespread of smartphones, thus turning a risk factor into a safety improvement chance and the opportunities offered by an urban monitoring & communication infrastructure. SOTIF can be improved thanks to the possibility of gathering information about the position of VRU through their smartphones that are connected to the urban infrastructure and thanks to the monitoring sensors of the urban infrastructure, thus providing vehicles with an enhanced "vision" of position and speed of VRUs. And this opportunity is true for VRUs that, can be alerted about potential risks of collision by properly managed warnings about the presence of dangerous vehicles in a wide range of situations including distracted VRUs and cases when symmetrically to what happens for vehicles, obstacles prevent vision and thus danger awareness. FS can be improved, as well, since the addition of the combination of smart devices in the hands of VRUs and urban monitoring and communication infrastructure provides vehicles with an additional (redundant) source of information to identify dangerous situation and therefore to provide increased fail-operational capabilities to the on-board vision systems.

Industrial Pilot 3 aims to a 50% reduction of collisions with VRUs and other traffic participants compared to what is achievable by human drivers. In terms of safety objectives, the Pilot 3 addresses SOTIF by demonstrating the functionality of VRUs detection when not visible with the vehicle perception system and VRUs' alerting in case vehicle approaching, and the FS by demonstrating a VRUs localization redundancy that, in case of vehicle on board perception system failure, can be obtained by the VRU detection provided by the urban infrastructure.

IV. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Definitely, large scale deployment of connectivity will be a game changer for road transport. It will enable to bridge the silos between the different stakeholders (e.g., vehicles, vulnerable road users, infrastructure operators), finally creating a more accurate and comprehensive understanding

about the full environment as well as mission from each participant. This enhanced information, in turn, will enable the creation of digital twin, creating the foundation for new range of services. In the context of this paper, the example of advanced navigation, HW map creation and accident preventions have been applied to three use cases, with the target to evaluate the respective impact in terms of mobility efficiency (reducing traffic jams, reducing energy consumption) and in terms of road safety (reducing number of accident, especially with vulnerable road users). During the next steps of the projects, the solutions will be deployed and evaluated in the described industrial pilots.

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